

Morena Tartari

University of Antwerp, Belgium

Change in the family field: reading disruption and its effects through Bourdieu

1. Introduction

Pierre Bourdieu (1996) applies his well-known concept of field also to the family. Family, like other fields described by his social theory, is characterized by reproduction and change even if Bourdieu's oeuvre does not offer a clearly-understandable description of the mechanisms that concern social change.

As a field, the family comprises dominant and dominated sections and an orthodox definition of reality that contends against heterodox definitions (Bourdieu 1977). Atkinson (2016) then extends Bourdieu's vision of the family as a field: he takes into account conflicts of interest, relations of power, and struggles that concern boundaries and membership, and indicates unexplored pathways for social research.

This article follows Atkinson's invitation to add empirical contributions to theoretically refining the idea of the family as a field of struggle. Furthermore, it aims to show that Bourdieu's work is not only concerned with reproduction (Jenkins 1982; 2014), but also with change and transformation (Costa 2006; Fowler 2020).

By analyzing the results of a transnational study on mothers' experiences with the judicial system during their transitions from double to single parenthood due to separation (Tartari 2019), in this paper, Bourdieu's conceptual tools will allow explaining the effects of the crisis and change in the contemporary family field. The paper outlines the conflicts within the field, the adaptations of

agents to these changes, the elements that persist after disruption and crisis, the costs they entail for mothers, and how—and to what extent—the transformative actions of the field are possible.

The results focus in particular on situations in which an element of family disruption is constituted by the ex-spouse's violence. These relational ruptures cause crises on social, economic, and biographical levels, highlighting the implications and collusion of mothers with the field to which they belong. Such impacts on the life trajectories of these mothers and their minor children have been analyzed through different approaches (see, for instance, Nieuwenhuis, Maldonado 2018; Bernardi, Mortelmans 2018), but an analysis through a Bourdieusan perspective lacks. The article aims to contribute to filling in this gap and takes into consideration also the influence of the other fields (e.g., the judicial one) on that of the family.

The path I propose in this article is as follows. I critically introduce the concepts of Bourdieu's social theory concerning family as a field and the critical perspectives on Bourdieu's thought which allow interpreting processes of crisis and change. I continue by presenting the methodology of the study. I then utilize these concepts and critical perspectives to inductively interpret the results that emerged from my research and to highlight elements of reproduction and change emerging from rupture and crisis, in dialogue with the literature that analyses contemporary family transformations. I conclude by proposing an examination of the aspects that allow reinterpreting Bourdieu's work as characterized by both reproduction and change and refining family as a field and, and by tracing suggestions for desirable future empirical contributions.

2. Family as field

Bourdieu's approach has received limited attention about its potential in analyzing the family as a field, its crisis, and changes. Furthermore, Bourdieu has been accused of being a reproductive theorist and of giving the family attention only as a conductor of the transmission of capital

(Morgan 1999, 21). On the contrary, his social theory grasps the power structures to which the family field is interconnected and its role not only in reproduction but also in the fractures of this social and cultural reproduction (Atkinson 2014, 45).

Family, like other fields, is a system of positions and relationships among positions. Bourdieu (1990a; 1990b) initially defined the family in terms of «practical kinship» or «the field of relationships that are constantly re-used», and which are not unrelated to conflicts of interest, resistances, tensions, and struggles over membership and boundaries.

For Bourdieu (1996), the family is a *reified* category, a collective principle of the construction of collective reality, which assumes its implicit descriptions and prescriptions—a *nomos*—that is learned through socialization. The family is therefore a principle rooted in the objectivity of social structures and the subjectivity of mental structures, so much so that it appears natural.

The structures of the family, such as kinship and social bodies, can only be perpetuated thanks to the symbolic and practical daily work of creating and maintaining the family feeling—the disposition to love, cohesion, and work—that often falls on the woman on the basis of the organization of tasks based on gender roles (*ibidem*, 22). The daily practices of family members are subject to the structure of power relations within the field in which male domination plays a predominant role. The family is one of the key sites of accumulation and intergenerational transmission of social, cultural, and economic capital.

Bourdieu does not fail to underline how, in the work of categorizing the family and its members, the State plays a fundamental role by favoring certain types of family organization and helping to reproduce the legitimacy of families that correspond to certain indicators of conformity, through the institutional discourses that circulate in the common sense (about the role of the State see the critical review of Rinaldi 2012).

Will Atkinson's work (2014, 224) presents the potential of Bourdiesian concepts to explain the crises and struggles of individuals who belong to the field of the contemporary family. Atkinson's contribution consists of developing the discussion concerning the constitutive elements of the

family as a field: its *doxa*, its internal struggles with respect to capitals, its borders, and its roots in a larger universe of family relationships. First, Atkinson makes it possible to place the family as a field in relation to other national and international fields of power (political, bureaucratic, economic, religious, intellectual, media, legal, scientific, etc.), which contribute to providing a legitimate definition of reality, causing a tension between orthodox and heterodox definitions of reality (Bourdieu 1977).

Such definitions of the family are dominated by the prevailing orthodox perspective offered by the Western world, which sees the family as the fundamental natural unit of society based on traditional gender roles (Atkinson 2014, 225). Within the family field, Atkinson identifies a struggle for an orthodox definition between the richest factions in terms of cultural capital (e.g., experts, therapists, and teachers) and the richest factions in terms of economic capital. The heterodox version is instead supported by a radical faction (Bourdieu 2001) that advocates non-consanguinity, non-heterosexuality, and non-nuclear definitions of family.

Atkinson identifies a dialectical relationship between material conditions and representations. This dialogue allows for reshaping the *doxa* and, therefore, continually questioning the definitions (for other critical contributions on this topic, see for instance Costa 2006, Singh 2022). Rooted in the shared experience of family members, there is also a family-specific *doxa* influenced by available capital, gendered dispositions, as well as expectations and anticipations—particularly those regarding the future of each member (Bourdieu, Passeron 1979, 12; Bourdieu 1990, 54). Finally, Atkinson highlights how conflict happens within the family field. Since the members possess different capitals, even symbolic ones, the family field consists of a system of objective and structural relations of domination (Bourdieu 1998, 68–70).

Each member also has power and capitals from other fields that affect the distribution of symbolic capital within the family (an example of this is male domination within the family, with its most manifest expression in domestic violence). These elements, with others like family trajectories, play a role in determining the structure and struggles of particular family fields, such as when new

members forcibly enter (Atkinson 2014, 229) or leave. Furthermore, in family fields, where the family doxa is strenuously defended and affirmed by parents who manage to have a united front, the struggles are reduced, and the final result is a reproduction of the social position. However, in fields where this does not happen and where orthodoxy and heterodoxy come into conflict, there can be ambivalence or rejection of the inheritance, thus generating trajectories and practices that deviate from the family doxa and generate a break with it (for examples about parents' expectations and children behavior, see Bourdieu 1999, Bourdieu 2000).

These threats to the family doxa become concrete when the boundaries of the family field are threatened or changed. For example, an absent father may not be perceived as playing a role in the field (Atkinson 2014, 230)—resulting in objective structures coming into conflict with subjective perceptions, which can have concrete effects on dispositions and family doxa through practices.

The literature that has devoted space to the application of Bourdieu's conceptual tools to the family as a field and family crises is scant. Studies related to one of the fields often linked to the family crisis, the legal one, are rare (e.g., Hacker 2008). Furthermore, neither Bourdieu nor Atkinson develop articulated reflections on the topic of change within the family field.

3. Conceptual tools to interpret family crises and change

Some contributions allow going beyond the “reproductive” focus and highlighting how social change is conceived by Bourdieu. The first line of contributions (McNay 1999; Adkins, Skeggs 2004; McLeod 2005; Kenwen, McLeod 2004) comes from a feminist re-reading of the possibilities that Bourdieu's thought offers to analyze social change. By analyzing the coexistence of change and continuity in gender relations and identities, McLeod (2005) explains how social change is something that does not emerge clearly from Bourdieu's oeuvre, but from his intellectual project. In particular, McLeod points out how habitus can be intended as a generative structure formed in a

dynamic relation with specific fields and not a fixed and imposed way of being (see also McNay 1999). Thus, habitus' creative potential and improvisation are underestimated. In addition, Bourdieu would neglect historical and cultural specificities and the dynamism of the relationship between habitus and field.

A second contribution (Costa 2006) aims to show how social change cannot be found in Bourdieu's social theory but in his public interventions. Costa poses emphasis on the habitus generative potential as well (see also Singh 2022). Furthermore, he highlights the need to take into consideration a temporal/historical perspective in approaching the habitus: the circumstances in which the habitus originally was modeled can be different from those in which the social agent acts. Then, the turn to a certain degree of awareness of the subject is analyzed as a factor of social change. Finally, the author's reflections on the role of intellectual and political fields in social change offer suggestions about how to interpret the intertwining of different fields in social transformation (see also Fram 2004).

Furthermore, among the tools proposed by Bourdieu, some are fundamental concepts to analyze the family systemic change in this paper.

First is the concept of *hysteresis* (Hardy 2014, 144). Bourdieu's analysis (2002; 1988; 1999) also «concerns the moments in which a crisis of the habitus (*hysteresis*) occurs in conjunction with structural transformations of the social space and of the different fields in which it is articulated in contemporary societies» (Pitzalis 2019, 30). In family disruptions, the organizing forces of the family field change, the aspects of everyday life in which practical kinship is exercised are missing, a sort of disruption is generated between field and habitus «in particular, when a field undergoes a major crisis and its regularities (even its rules) are profoundly changed» (Bourdieu 2000, 160). Hysteresis represents «a mismatch between two elements which were previously coordinated» and «the possibility of change which is permanent and irreversible» (Hardy 2014, 128). Field and habitus are conceived as dependent elements, in interaction between them (see, for instance, McLeod 2004), and hysteresis happens where and when habitus fails in its attempt to act in line

with the field in which it usually operates, it, therefore, finds itself disconnected from the field in which assumptions change, and nothing can be taken for granted anymore (Bourdieu, 1990a; Strand, Lizardo 2017; Graham 2020). This new condition generated by the lack of synchrony between habitus and the positions available in the field brings with it opportunities and risks (Bourdieu, 2015). Only agents who have privileged positions—a favorable combination of capitals—will be able to easily overcome the crisis, seize the opportunities, and reduce the risks of a changing trajectory. Where then the habitus assumes a practical awareness (Costa 2006) of the potential of the situation, it allows the agent to manipulate the situation to his own advantage (Cronin 1996, 65). It enables us to detect crises within a field or between different fields. However, its application to the family field is only hinted at. Anyway, hysteresis is not a concept free from criticisms. For example, King (2000, 427-8) argues that the hysteresis effect does not suffice to explain social change, but, due to the inflexibility of the habitus, only sidesteps it. Individuals do not have enough creative force to rethink the principles of their actions and change their inflexible habituses. Therefore, King states that social change can only be intrinsic to Bourdieu's practical theory and can only happen through individuals' social exchanges, interactions, and negotiations. Another conceptual tool to be taken into consideration in the analysis of crises in the family field is *co-implication* or *collusion* with the field (Pitzalis 2019). Assuming that habitus allows the production of practices that are able to adapt to the social order that produces them, an active co-implication of the agent in the social space follows, also described by Bourdieu as *forced collusion* with the group to which they belong. This explanation, applicable to different fields, capacitates us to understand the functioning of the relationship between habitus and the family field.

Habitus has the practical experience of the group, its doing, and its being to the point of incorporating its rules without questioning them. It is, therefore, the fruit and foundation of a complicity—integration into a certain social space and the sharing of a certain doxa—or of an implicit collusion (*ibidem*, 40) between all members of the field. Co-implication in the field is therefore a form of solidarity with the field itself and of conversion to the dominant logic of the

field. In this game of forces, agents—even when they try to change the organization of the field and its rules—can end up reproducing its structural logic due to the internalized dispositions that guide their actions (*ibidem*), even during and after conflicts.

The accomplice contenders (Bourdieu 1984, 149) may be the dominated and may not be able to put into practice rules other than those already learned within the field, thus failing to subvert the order. An example of a figure of complicity (Pitzalis 2019, 39-40) is that of the dominated woman, which has sparked heated debate in feminist literature (e.g., Butler 1999; Lovell 2000) since Bourdieu describes the dominated woman as an accomplice of male domination. However, this co-implication or collusion should not be understood in a moral sense but merely in a descriptive one. In the relational dialectical process between continuity and change in the field, forms of resistance also emerge. They are not fractures concerning the logic of the field but are «forms of commitment» and of «implication» that take place within a given field and that can contribute to accelerating its transformation and modifying its relations of strength or resources (Pitzalis 2019, 31). Casey's study (2021) on single mothers and acts of resistance against the welfare-to-work policy describes the everyday forms of resistance of single mothers against symbolic violence and domination and their efforts in converting individual forms of resistance into collective action.

The perspectives on social change in Bourdieu's theory and the above-mentioned tools will be discussed through the results of the study that I conducted.

4. The research study: investigating family fractures and their effects

The study STRESS-Mums (see Tartari 2019) is a mixed-method study carried out by using the approach of Institutional Ethnography or IE (Smith 2005) and developed by taking into account the most recent literature on single parents and their trajectories after separation or divorce (Nieuwenhuis, Maldonado 2018; Bernardi, Mortelmans 2018). The literature highlighted a gap

concerning the study of how judicial institutions rule mothers everyday life and shape future lone parents' future trajectories during that crucial period of transition and transformation of the family due to partners' separation (Ruspini 2013; Mortelmans 2020; Mortelmans 2021) and how lone mothers try to negotiate and resist to the definitions imposed by the institutions (Coltrane, Adams 2003; Emery 2013). Therefore, the study aims to start filling in this gap. Even if framed by the materialist approach of Institutional Ethnography, the research study took into consideration – as sensitizing concepts – the reflection of Bourdieu and Atkinsons on the family as a field. In particular, the study aimed to investigate how mothers, in their interactions with the judicial system, negotiate the orthodox definition of family with the heterodox definitions that they propose and embody.

By following the approach of IE, the study chose to take into consideration mothers' standpoints because of their historical position of subordination within the family field (Smith 1987; Smith 1990; DeVault 1990; Bourdieu 2001; Bimbi 2014). Furthermore, studies often show that, after the separation, women who are single parents live with worse conditions than those of their ex-partners because of their weaker economic, cultural, and social capitals (for a review of studies at a European level, see Tartari 2022; Nieuwenhuis 2020; Kreyenfeld, Trappe 2020).

The study was conducted in four European countries: Italy, Spain, Belgium, and the UK. However, in this article, only accounts from Italian, Belgian, and Spanish fieldwork are used, as these countries have similar socio-cultural aspects concerning the discourse relating to the family and the legal changes that concern it, unlike the fieldwork conducted in the UK. For instance, the law that rules children custody was updated in similar years (about the middle of the 2000s) in all three countries by introducing the children shared custody by default (even in case of severe domestic violence episodes) and leaving the application of sole custody to very rare cases.

In these three countries, I conducted 50 in-depth interviews: 36 with lone mothers (12 for each country) and 14 with professionals (lawyers, court-appointed experts, gender specialists) belonging to the judiciary field (5 in Belgium, 4 in Spain, 5 in Italy). The criterion of saturation shaped the

size of the sample and sub-samples. It is a methodological hint from Grounded Theory and utilized also in Institutional Ethnography. In addition to the interviews, I collected and analyzed documents from civil proceedings and multidisciplinary professionals' conferences, and I conducted photo-voice activities with single mothers in each of these countries. Mothers were involved in two rounds of interviews: the first, an in-depth interview that explored the social dynamics of their separation, how judicial institutions ruled their experience and trajectory, the forms of resistance these women enacted, how they negotiated change and heterodox definitions; the second, an in-depth interview that questioned the documents (e.g., legal petitions) that ruled their experience of separation more thoroughly.

To study the interface of the interactions between mothers and judicial institutions, and the ruling discourses from those institutions, a small sample of professionals were recruited. Professionals were interviewed by the Interview to the Double technique (Oddone, Re, Briante 1977; Nicolini 2009). Interviews were conducted by using the Italian language in Italy, and the Spanish language in Spain. In Belgium, when the interviewees were fluent in English, I used the English language, but when interviewees did not speak fluently English I conducted the interviews in Dutch with the help of a mother-tongue translator previously trained. The interviews usually lasted from one hour to two hours. The study received ethical approval before its start. Participants were overtly informed about the aims of the study.

Participants were initially recruited by advertising the research study on social media and through different institutions (e.g., schools, universities, social and health services) and then by snowballing sampling. The first sampling criterion concerned mothers' judicial choice to resist the mainstream prescriptions about children's custody: I recruited mothers who filed a request for sole custody of their children to the court. The second criterion concerned social class in order to investigate how experiences and practices differ in relation to different mothers' habituses. At the end of the interview, I asked the interviewees for providing socio-demographic data. In addition, I asked them information about their objective and subjective position with regard to economic capital.

The age of the mothers interviewed varies from 30 to 55. In each sub-sample, 50% of the mothers belong to the working class and 50% to the middle class. In each sub-sample, 20-30% of the mothers were immigrants (from Central European countries in Italy, from South American countries in Spain, from North Africa in Belgium). The length of the marriage varies from 20 to 3 years. The age of children varies from 3 to 17 and, on average, interviewees had two children born before the separation. About 70% of the mothers were victims of physical, economical, and/or emotional violence. About 40% had former partners sentenced for Intimate Partner Violence (IPV). Professionals selected were working in the same courts where the mothers had initiated and concluded the separation procedure. Professionals interviewed had at least ten years of experience within the judicial field or as gender specialists.

For the purpose of this paper, the analysis is based on the interviews collected from mothers and professionals. A discussion based on the interpretative elements made available by the IE is omitted and will be developed in a separate essay. The analysis, conducted by NVivo, aimed to map out the objective structures of the field in terms of forms of power to analyze the positions of the actors in the field relative to the power relations of the field and to analyze the habitus of the actors to identify not only how their action is limited by the power relations of the field (Grenfell 2014, 73) but also how change is possible.

5. Family field's crises: emblematic cases from the fieldwork

This section starts with an overview of sociodemographic data. Then, I will draw on three emblematic cases – one from each country – in dialogue with the literature concerning family sociology, Bourdieu's conceptual tools, which allow analyzing crisis and change. I will take into account the characteristics of the conflicts within the family field and the adaptations of the agents to these conflicts; the elements that persist after disruption and the costs they entail for mothers;

how—and to what extent—the transformative actions of the field are possible. These emblematic cases can also be considered as ideal types, which summarize elements very frequently pointed out by the results. The description of these ideal types will be accompanied by the description of the interface of interactions with the judicial professionals and gender specialists to show how different fields affected the family field and its members. This discussion does not aim to be an exhaustive analysis of the research results, but it aims to utilize some results to show how Bourdieu's intellectual project can be applied to explain social change.

These mothers' socio-demographic data allows understanding their positions in the family field. They often had left the job market or reduced work time to raise and care for children; often this choice was supported and suggested by the partner himself. Therefore, these mothers often had less significant economic capital in comparison with their partners at the moment of the family disruption. Their family field had been organized around traditional gender roles, without particular relation with the age, but in relation with the education level (i.e., lowest levels frequently correspond with traditional roles) and in a similar way in all countries.

Mothers with psychological abuse experience often had been tolerating abusive behaviors from the partner for years up to the moment in which that behavior crossed the threshold of what they could endure (e.g., they were battered more violently than usual or at the presence of their children). Mothers without that experience reported that the trigger event was an unexpected betrayal from the partner, forms of economic or emotional abuse towards them and/or their children. To not lose their privileges within the field and protect their children's economic and social capitals, these mothers tried to *adapt* and *resist* as much as possible and to delay the separation or the idea of the separation. This is a very frequent account and it finds support from the literature (McDonald-Harker 2016; Sanz-Barbero et al. 2018; Weil et al. 2018). Furthermore, they sometimes tried to resist because they believed that their parents or relatives would have never given them their support for and after the separation. The fear of the risks of poverty was described in particular by women with a lower class, higher number of children, and weak social capital. Then, the

interviewees reported various after-separation problems (e.g., family/work balance, health, isolation) congruent with the literature (e.g., Bernardi, Mortelmans 2018). For all of them, separation, regardless of the causes, meant entering a phase of *dis-grace* (Atkinson 2021) from which they emerged with paths that sometimes lasted several years after the dispersion of many forms of capital accumulated during the marriage. The state of disgrace generated by divorce or separation brought them to a downward trend in social mobility, and this is coherent with the data that the literature usually shows for women (Grella 1990; Nieuwenhuis, Maldonado 2018; Thielemans, Mortelmans 2021). Often, these crises in the family field generated *negative* social capital for women who previously relied on the social capital of their partners. Many of them began a phase of more or less acute social or economic suffering and have had to seek help and support in social welfare. Sometimes, a way out of this condition – as the literature indicates – was offered by repartnering (e.g., Jansen, Mortelmans, Snoeckx 2009; Pasteels, Mortelmans 2015). However, most of the women interviewed are still alone a few years after the separation due to having to carry alone the burden of leading the family. In fact, a lack of leisure time seems due to intensive parenting, a transformation of parenting that has taken place in recent decades. Congruently with this social transformation supported by the richest factions in terms of cultural capital (e.g., experts), these mothers experienced pressure towards forms of intensive parenting in order to be perceived as more adequate mothers (for a discussion on intensive parenting see: Shirani, Henwood, Coltart 2012; Faircloth 2014; Smyth, Craig, 2017; Fargion 2021), in particular when they were under evaluation by the court.

An emblematic case from Italy

Bruna (52), mother of three teenagers, has a low level of education and comes from a working-class family. Her husband – who belongs to the working class as well – physically and emotionally mistreated her and their children for many years and carried out several assassination attempts aimed at her. Brunas's story offers an example of the cost of colluding and converting to field logic.

However, her actions also represent a form of resistance to the influence of fields outside the family. Set in a patriarchal culture, not employed for years by choice of her husband—who preferred her to take care of their children—Bruna had never taken into consideration the idea of separation even after years of violence. Her collusion with the family field was so profound that it prevented her from escaping to safety.

In the last 15 days, I have seen death... We were at home [on vacation] and therefore he [my husband] had more chances of attacking us... so I would take the children and take them out of the house to keep them away from him... But he had already planned our end... [...] The Carabinieri [police officer] who listened to my story told me, «If you don't report it, I have to do it for a matter of responsibility because there are minors involved». [...] At that point, I said, «I'll do it, because I have to be the one to protect my children and he is not». But I [didn't go] there to file a complaint but to figure out what to do. At that moment, *I was no longer*. [From then on I canceled myself!] I only made it to protect my children... I was alone, scorched earth around... [...] I was a fly inside its web and I could do nothing but wait for the spider to come and eat me. I had no awareness of what would happen next, I'm telling the truth. [...] [she is moved] I had no idea what would have happened... I did it only for my children... *If I had been alone [without my children], he would have quietly killed me...* Instead: only the mother is left and she managed to rescue her children... damaged, wounded, with stumps... but in safety... [Italian fieldwork, Interview n. 2]

What Bruna explained is that if it had not been to save her children from physical injuries and mental harm), she—to remain within the family field—would never have chosen to break with the field through an explicit act, such as a report to the police. This collusion was also supported by his parents, to whom she had never had the strength to *confess* that she was a victim of violence because, as she explained, their *family spirit* would not have allowed them to understand the situation in which she lived. What her family – in particular her mother – were suggesting concerned a form of *adaptation* and, thus, of reproduction of the logic of the field: a kind of

intergenerational perpetuation of acceptance of husbands' violence in exchange for a stable and socially recognized role – the wife – and a stable economic income.

During and after their separation, Bruna and her husband continued to struggle to impose an orthodox definition of the family field, which is coherent with their dispositions. The interference of the legal field at the beginning of their separation worked in the direction of breaking the collusion, ending the violence, and imposing new balances.

The conversion of Bruna to the judicial field logic has, for her, a high cost, so high as to compel her to admit that she had to *cancel* herself to submit herself to it, with the purpose of protecting her children. Furthermore, the psychological support that Bruna received from the professionals of a specialized center for women victims of violence aimed to bring her not only psychological but even social *awareness* about her situation of crisis and her collusion. The concept of collusion or co-implication is a valuable tool as an element that works at an objective, structural level and not at a subjective level.

During and after separation, Bruna experienced what can be described as hysteresis: a crisis of her habitus in conjunction with structural transformations of the social space. Friends and relatives isolated her, she left home with children to go to a specialized shelter and lost the right to live in the family home for many months. At the same time, after she left, she started understanding that institutions have not been supporting completely her choice, posing her in a condition of continuous evaluation by social services and mental health experts and a condition of fear because her husband was kept free for several years before the imprisonment and stalked her and children. He has the right to visit children with monitored meetings nevertheless children did not want to meet him. This prescription from the legal system in this emblematic case – as described by a lawyer interviewed – can be considered a form of support of the orthodox discourse for the family field. In the case of Bruna, like in other cases, during the family evaluation by the court, this discourse has been associated with threats by social workers (in other cases by court-appointed experts) of «taking her children away from her» if she does not support children's contacts with their father. This kind of

orthodox discourse that protects traditional forms of family even in case of severe violence was reported also by other judicial professionals.

Bruna's story, like many other accounts, shows how institutions can support the reproduction of the logic of the orthodox family definition at two levels: first, that of the specific family field, and second, that of the field of power that crosses the legal field, the economic field and the intellectual field, through institutionally legitimized forms of prescription and ban. These forms of prescription and ban are aimed at guaranteeing a social order through the regulation of the family in an orthodox sense, even after the rupture of the separation. The judicial field exerts forms of limitation of parents' rights against those parents who deviate from or reject such prescriptions.

Interviews from the Italian fieldwork point out a problem that is always highlighted by gender specialists: there is a disconnection between the needs of mothers and judicial practices, even after the recent legislative changes to protect women who are victims of violence (Pisanu, Sdau 2020; D.i.Re 2020; D.i.Re. 2021). Gender specialists often highlight that the adherence of the justice system to a discourse that supports the orthodox definition of the family is such that it does not allow elaborating a specific custody procedure to protect mothers and minors in case of IPV: it continues instead to protect mainly fathers. In fact, an Italian gender specialist who coordinates a shelter for women victims of IPV stated:

Then, also a whole series of prejudices that we carry within us regarding what it means to be a good mother and a good father with criteria that are not the same, and are not the same even in the evaluation phase: the woman we follow at the center and who she is on a path to escape from violence and that even a mother of minor children is called to answer a dozen tasks: she has to protect herself but she has to protect her children, she has to work but she has to dedicate quality time to her children, she has to go to the psychologist, she has to go to the social worker, she has to bring the children for evaluation, she has to accompany them to protected meetings, she doesn't have to discredit the image of the father, she must facilitate the relationship with the father, she must have economic availability to meet the needs of the children, she must not stay too

long in a shelter because it is not a healthy environment for children, etc. The father is asked to show up on time for meetings, to bring a present to the children, and to spend an hour in the company of the children without having to answer any tasks, and therefore it is just an hour of fun with the children. So, on the scale these two plates have very different weights. [...] [But] this is also in the mind of [professionals and social workers] because the work of caring for children in our country is attributed to the mother, it is the responsibility of the mother, it is the mother who is responsible for it; the father is asked much less. The father is asked not to be something. The mother is asked to be a hundred things.

Lawyers interviewed confirmed this situation even if they stated – in a contradictory way – that the law on children's custody works properly. However, the law on children custody does not mention how to act in these specific cases of IPV.

It should be noted that the Italian sample comes from an area of north-eastern Italy with conservative family values, in which changes related to traditional gender roles in the family struggle to be realized, and women often live in a condition of subordination within the family field even if often invisible (Bimbi, Trifiletti 2006; Ruspini 2015; Crespi et al. 2015).

A social and cultural change is proposed by the groups of gender specialists who manage shelters for women (see also D.i.Re 2020). However, their proposal struggles to be fully accepted at the institutional level and a micro-social level. Women seem to be able to achieve real change only after the disorienting experience of hysteresis.

In the case of Bruna, social change happened through two dynamics. First, at an intergenerational level: there is a rupture between her and her mother's dispositions and biographical experiences due to her choice to not accept the violence that instead was acceptable for her mother. Second, at an inter-field level: social change comes from the possibilities for Bruna to cross different fields and speak with different people who brought her awareness and the power to resist and adopt a heterodox definition of family.

Bruna's change, as well as many of the other interviewees of the Italian sample, is achieved thanks to the political commitment and action of professionals of the shelters for women who fight violence at a microsocial level and an institutional level. Bruna found a job position after years outside the job market and raise her children alone, without economic support from their father. However, with exception of the shelter's social network, she lives in a condition of marginalization, in conflict with the social services, and isolated from old friends who have never approved her separation.

An emblematic case from Spain

The Spanish sample of mothers presents a higher degree of education in comparison to the Italian one (all interviewees have a university degree), but a lower level of economic capital: in other words, despite the higher level of education, many interviewees belong to the working class. In comparison to the Italian one, the Spanish sample includes a smaller number of reports for domestic violence but a higher number of economic problems after the disruption. However, the higher education level allowed these women to cross different fields easily and to develop forms of awareness of the dominant/orthodox definitions more quickly.

The emblematic case is that of Carmen – a 49-year-old Spanish artist – that allows understanding better hysteresis, the process of change by developing awareness and by individual proactive choice thanks to her cultural capital. She found herself involved in various civil and criminal proceedings and in serious economic difficulties after the breakup of the relationship by her partner, who was the father of her two young children. The core of her story is in the following excerpt.

The first months after the separation, he was present with the children, but the moment the other person [the new partner] appeared, the problems started. She wanted to take on the role of mother for my children. I started to protest, and things got complicated and suddenly. The father stopped paying the agreed maintenance. I was at home with two very young children; at that time, I worked very

sporadically. [...] Financially, it was tremendous. The bank made me a loan of 25 thousand euros, which I am still paying. With the loan, I managed to survive, to support myself for a year and a half. You can imagine the trauma in that moment. He wanted custody of the children. That's where the *judicial war* unilaterally started because I didn't want to. It was very traumatic. It has been, I think, five long years of a lot of fear. I felt very lonely and very attached because the father's economic power is very high, not like mine. [...] I thought that, with the fact that he was powerful, I couldn't do anything about it. My son was totally dominated by his father and did not want to see me—my daughter almost the same. It was very very difficult, very painful. Then, in the end, after all the judicial process, to my surprise [the court] did not agree with him. They wrote that as a father he is very authoritarian, that he does not like to be contradicted, [and] that he is a manipulative person.

[Spanish fieldwork, Interview n. 8]

To confirm his position of dominance and authority within the field, Carmen's husband –an artist with a considerable income – started several legal battles against Carmen and asked for children's sole custody, which the court denied after the evaluation of his personality. By the way, when fathers or mothers ask for sole custody trying to modify the force field in a way different from that “normally” represented, the evaluation of parents' responsibilities and personality by court-appointed experts (usually psychologists or psychiatrists) is often requested by the judge. This kind of practice is non-homogenous among countries. Italy and Spain often apply this kind of in-court evaluation, but in Belgium, even if possible by law, this practice is often avoided. Spanish and Italian interviewees highlight problems and contradictions of in-court evaluation procedure that often reproduces what the law states in terms of custody. A Spanish court-appointed expert described as frequent the situations in which she is invited by lawyers to explain children's needs in order to counter the requests for sole custody filed by fathers in conflictual separations, like in Carmen's one. In these cases, courts often seem to aim to reproduce what the law indicates (shared custody) as a default solution by defining as conflictual couples those couples which did not reach a non-consensual separation but started one or more legal proceedings. This label of “conflictual”

couple, as explained by a recent study of Bertelsen (2021), does not allow to distinguish between real needs of sole custody, different reasons of the parents, particularities of the situations, but it does impose an orthodox definition without an attempt to see the heterodoxies which could emerge from the crisis.

Furthermore, Carmen's husband acted his power in the family field even affecting Carmen working trajectory. The violence he exercised against Carmen concerns the areas of her life in which she has less capital than him: the economic and social capitals. Carmen explained:

He is a famous artist and has come to influence my work. After the separation, I no longer worked as an artist. Look at what his influence has been in this regard, not only a sexist violence on his part but also a social violence. [Spanish fieldwork, Interview n. 8]

As the case of Carmen shows, separations of partners can generate exceedingly noticeable changes between the previous and subsequent conditions in the family field. As long as all the actors continue to collaborate even after the separation—acting *as if*—the field does not undergo excessive changes in the relations between the forces that compose it. This is not the case with *hysteresis*.

The changes in which hysteresis occurs are sudden—non-gradual—changes in which the discrepancies become relevant; there is a sense of being *out of time and place*, a failure to adapt to how circumstances are changing. The ways in which the habitus will evolve are unpredictable, and the positioning of the individual in the field is indeterminate (Hardy 2014, 127). The displacement between habitus and field has an effect on the structure of the field itself (*ibidem*). This is the case for Carmen and for many other interviewees who, to varying degrees and nuances, experienced these discrepancies. The misalignment between habitus and field sometimes becomes traumatic for parents and children: a frequent situation is that of economic suffering.

However, a strength for Carmen is her awareness of the violence she suffers and of the adaptation strategies she can implement after the fracture to realign habitus and field. If other women with a

lower education degree have fewer possibilities to leave the relationship with the dominant and to restructure it or they need more time to do it, usually interviewees with a more developed cultural capital have more “tools” in their toolbox.

Much of the “work” that mothers like Carmen did during the contact with the courts aimed to ensure economic rights to their children in an immediate and future perspective. In fact, parents represent their children as «heirs» (Pitzalis 2019, 33), but separation undermines the investment and expectations of parents. Risk society makes children precious and invaluable heirs (Zelizer 1994). However, the trajectory prefigured for the heir and supported by the family as a collective enterprise is undermined by the separation. After the separation, in fact, the heir could no longer access the same capitals. Family is no longer a unit that guarantees expected reproduction, and each of the parents can start a struggle to align the child’s trajectory with their expectations in competition with the other parent, to reconfigure forces and change within the family field. There is, therefore, again a mismatch concerning the starting conditions, the expectations of the members, and the reality of the field.

Sometimes, in an attempt to preserve family doxa and the forces within the field unaltered, parents seek collaboration and continuity as parents even when they are no longer a couple. However, this is not always the result of the crisis. As with school failures (Pitzalis 2019, 34), divorce is also a «source of frustration and split», since it produces ambivalent habituses, which question the family field’s uniqueness, the taken for granted doxa, and the consistency of members’ identity and trajectory. The imagined heir can therefore no longer be such an heir and this colludes with the fears and anxieties of parents about risks and appropriate parenting practices (Beck, Beck-Gernsheim 1995). Many interviewees – as we will see from the Belgian one – focus on the field of forces in which their children are, as heirs, and the expectations and anxieties of single mothers in raising their children as “proper” heirs. This kind of expectations and anxieties comes from experts’ discourses on risks and intensive parenting discourses, which find followers also among many

experts. The requests for children's allowances by the mothers often aim to fill in the gap between expected and real trajectories for the heir.

Even if Spanish mothers criticize courts' work to a lesser extent, one of the leitmotifs of the interviews collected was the lack of recognition by the court of the influence that the partner had on life and career choices before and after the separation. During their marriage, many of the interviewees had given up a job to look after their families and children, adjusting to adhering to an orthodox role and accepting living with an evident inequality of economic capital compared to the husband. At the time of separation, the former partner a few times asks for sole custody but often tries to obtain shared custody with the arrangement of children at 50% of the time and expenses, even if he had never previously looked after the children or shown interest in their lives.

Lawyers and mothers interviewed explain that this allows fathers to avoid paying a maintenance allowance to the mother for their children. Sometimes professionals commented that the 50% division is in favor of the mother who works. However, mothers feel of being victims of "institutional violence", as they are not recognized for the difficulties that they will encounter in entering the world of work after years of not being involved in it or alone with young children. In other words, mothers' full-time commitment within the family in previous years and the fact that this was often a choice imposed by the partner who had greater economic and symbolic capital is taken for granted and not taken into account during courts' decisions. These accounts are common to all three countries and interviews even if these countries have different policies to support single parents.

An emblematic case from Belgium

This interview exemplifies the process of co-implication within the family field and the influence from other fields that can generate change or reproduction.

Lydia is a 38-year-old mother of a 4-year-old daughter, from the middle class and with a university degree. She comes from a family with traditional gender roles. Her partner left home a few months

after the birth of their daughter. He refused any agreement with Lydia for maintenance and family mediation for their daughter. He found another partner, and always showed no interest in having contact with the daughter.

Lydia kept the separation hidden for months from family, friends, and acquaintances. In doing so, she shows complicity with the field and an attempt to reproduce the traditional gender roles and conventional representations of parenthood and parenting that come from her family. The way she represents the father figure comes from that cultural inheritance. However, the reality in which she lives in shows an absent father who risked losing rights of visit and custody and who pretended to change behavior only when she filed an issue at the local court.

Since their separation, Lydia has been distressed that the absence of the father figure could cause mental issues for her daughter. During the interview, she shows clearly her worries and fear regarding the trajectory of her daughter as an heir. This is the main reason she hired a lawyer and started civil proceedings. Her anxieties about how to be a good parent were confirmed by a popular psychological book written by a Belgian psychologist and family mediator, as she explains:

The title of the book is something like «A week to mom and a week to dad. What children really need in a divorce». I was really thinking: «We need to do it 50/50 because that will be good for our daughter. If we don't split it equally, she will turn into a monster or something else». [...] *I felt so guilty for my daughter!* [...] [The lawyer] suggested to me to read [in-depth] that book for *other* insights about *co-parenting*, that it doesn't have to be 50/50 in every situation. [...] And [at the court hearing], he [the ex-partner] wanted a 50/50 agreement on paper. On paper! And then, [after the hearing] he said: «I will show up whenever I feel like it». I didn't realize it immediately because I was focused on the calendars [the organization of the father's visit to the child]. But when we left, my lawyer said: «Wow, it's so crazy of him to say that to the judge, to ask 50/50, because then he would also get 50% of the child allowance». [...]

Note by the interviewer: Later, in another part of the interview, the mother began to cry and she explained to me that, as she has not been able to ensure a 50/50 real agreement; every day she is worried about the psychological wellbeing of her daughter. [Belgian fieldwork, interview n. 8]

In this representation, being a good parent means to be an intensive mother and to allow the father to be an intensive parent through co-parenting. Many other interviewees in all three countries shared this representation, which correspond to the current conception of parenting in many Western countries (Faircloth 2014; Faircloth, Murray 2015; Fargion 2021). If parents do not realize this prescription from the experts, the heir will become *defective* because of mothers' behavior and field disruption (see also Geinger et al. 2014). Following these prescriptions, Lydia accepts the compromise to come to terms with the judicial field that suggests 50/50 agreements by default, and with an abusive former partner rather than risk the heir being compromised. Despite the partner's inappropriate and abusive behavior, Lydia does not accept being alone in raising her daughter to not lose the symbolic capital of the father figure. Lydia colludes with the orthodox definition from the family field in an attempt to preserve some of its logic, including protecting the imagined trajectory of the heir. She accepts the logic that the father figure is an indisputable symbolic capital, and fails to recognize that he could not represent that capital and he is utilizing strategies to maintain the forces of the field in his favor. In other words, she fails to *become aware* of the heterodoxy that emerged from the crisis in favor of an orthodox representation of the family. Therefore, the lawyer tried to show her the effects of collusion with the logic of the family field and with the ways of power relations imposed by the former partner, and to explain to her that co-parenting has many nuances and facets other than the 50/50 discourse.

As the lawyer suggests, change is possible by becoming aware of ex-partner strategies and failures and, by becoming aware that heterodox definitions can be acceptable. This kind of awareness in Lydia emerges from the contacts with the legal field. However, this is not always the case. When lawyers are co-implicated with orthodox definitions, they support the reproduction of the field logic.

Therefore, when lawyers cross the boundaries of the legal field and catch up on ideas from different fields, like the intellectual/political one, show their potential for collecting the heterodoxy emerging from the crisis and generating change.

Three lawyers interviewed in Belgium explained that in comparison to the Italian courts, the Belgian courts often apply shared custody by default even in conflictual and complicated cases, without investigations by experts (only by social workers in very rare cases) and this represents a real limit to understand the complexity of some situations. Mothers reported that they had a very limited time to plead their causes and explain facts during court hearings. From the mothers' standpoints, this kind of organization of the judicial evaluation confirms an orthodox vision of the family when it is formed by heterosexual couples. Even mothers in IPV cases have experience of custodial arrangements applied by default like in Italy. In this scenario, the role of the lawyer as a "reader" who translates the law to the mother/client by explaining it through a simple and understandable language, is crucial. Lawyers have the role of accompanying their clients to a field other than family, to explain strategies to navigate these fields, to promote awareness and change of the family field.

After her lawyer's explanations, Lydia reinterpreted the role and strategies of her ex-partner and tried to find different meanings to the situation in which she lives with her daughter. Even if during the interview she still shows ambivalence and co-implication, she is able to a double vision about her situation thanks to this form of awareness developed by crossing the fields. This kind of awareness – as explained by a gender specialist interviewed in Belgium – is even more difficult to reach for mothers who come from different cultures and social backgrounds (with a lower degree of education and fewer possibilities to cross the fields). For this reason, thanks to her political activity this gender specialist established a program implemented by the local social services with the aim to empower single mothers with sole custody and who need to cancel violence from their family doxa, avoid marginalization due to poverty, and improve and change their social conditions. Once more

the interpretations offered by McLeod (2005) and Fram (2004) on the potential of Bourdieu's social theory in interpreting change are valuable.

6. Conclusion. Family field, from orthodoxy to heterodoxy.

This paper aims to refine the concept of the family field and to show that by utilizing Bourdieu's social theory, not only reproduction but also change can be investigated and interpreted. Even if Bourdieu's oeuvre has limits in explaining change, his intellectual project has a wider potential to interpret social change (McLeod 2005; Costa 2006).

Data from my research project allowed analysing the family field and showing how processes of change happen after family disruption, the struggle between the taken-for-granted family doxa, and heterodox definitions. The results and the three emblematic cases show how Bourdieu's theoretical tools can be applied and reinterpreted through critical contributions from different authors. Findings show that change can happen as follows.

First, by *moving across different fields* (see also: McNay 1999, 107; McLeod, 2005, 21). This means, in other words, that family orthodox definitions can change by having experience with and by intersecting other fields. This allows improving social agents' knowledge and opportunities, challenging their dispositions, rejecting or supporting family doxa. This is the case of all three interviewees, which, with different degrees, have the opportunity to cross the fields, in particular the legal and intellectual ones, and to collect possibilities of dissonance and disjunctions, which produce differentiation and change. This interpretation highlights the role of secondary socialization and interactions between individuals and fields (interpretation also supported by King 2000, 429-30) to change the field logics and dispositions.

Second, by *adaptation after hysteresis* (see Pitzalis 2019), as shown by different cases. Social agents can experience hysteresis when their habitus and their related doxa are no longer able to

orient them in their daily life. Family doxa that was taken for granted until that moment, is now questioned and suspended. From the crisis, heterodoxy can emerge as an alternative doxa. Therefore, habitus can show its creative potential in order to accept or reject doxa, or gradually change it (Fram 2004, 556). Even if not all authors agree with considering hysteresis as a sufficient mechanism to explain crisis and change – for instance, King (2000, 428) points out that habitus is “caged” in its definition and blocks any change – results show that this can be seen as a formal limit of Bourdieu’s oeuvre, which theory potentials have not yet been entirely developed.

Finally, change can be reached by *individuals’ innovative acts*, which leave room for creativity, imagination, improvisation, reflexive insights, and innovation. Innovative acts can start in resistance within the field, generated by hysteresis, and can be found in different cases with different nuances in my research (see also see Pitzalis 2019; McLeod 2005). These acts can be investigated at a micro-social level but can be envisioned at a macro level as *political acts / public statements* based, for instance, on class awareness (Costa 2006, 887-91). Awareness is defined as something able to question one’s principles. Therefore, change can be supported by reaching awareness individually and collectively, and by rejecting the orthodoxy or mainstream assumptions (Bourdieu 1977, 164–71). From the findings, examples of innovative acts can be found in mothers' and gender specialists' accounts, which explain the process of affirmation of heterodoxy.

However, as argued also by McLeod (2005), the issue is not simply whether habitus or other theoretical tools can explain individuals’ acts of adaptation, resistance or change, ‘but whether Bourdieu’s conceptual framework is adequate for theorizing large-scale social/historical shifts or epochal change’. As stated above, Bourdieu’s intellectual project offers the premises to explain large-scale social shifts in the family field, even if his written oeuvre does not develop entirely and in a detailed way such premises.

What can be observed in regard to family field and doxa is how our contemporaneity, its historical/societal contexts, and changes affect family field objective structures and agents’ subjective dispositions, individuals’ acts of adaptation, resistance, or change.

The crisis of the couple and then the conditions of single parents can be linked with the crisis and the structural transformation of society. According to family historians (e.g., Coontz 2004, 974-5) and sociologists (e.g., Nieuwenhuis, Maldonado 2018), even if separation and single parenthood have many precedents in history, they have never coexisted neither with the right of women to take the initiative in separation/divorce, in asking for alimonies, in supporting themselves and their children through their work, in living without ties with the family of origin or a partner; nor with the affirmation of legal rights from unmarried hetero-sexual couples and same-sex partners. At the same time, the transformation of the job market (and rights for women in joining it) and gender roles (or at least, requests for changing traditional roles) have challenged the power relations within the family field and how people's rights and responsibilities are perceived based on biology and gender (see also: Butler 1990; Atkinson 2014; Ruspini 2015; Naldini et al. 2018). These epochal transformations have been reinterpreted by sections of the legal and intellectual fields, with reactions as, for instance, an increase in familism and orthodox views of family life. Someone interprets this resurgence of familism 'as a patriarchal backlash' in response to situations of structural changes in gender relations and the failure in maintaining symbolic dominance within the field (e.g., Grzyb 2016, 1043). This would explain the dynamics of violence against women within the family (e.g., Bimbi 2014; Sanz-Barbero et al. 2018; Weil, Corradi, Naudi 2018). At the same time, the transformation of parenting cultures and definitions of "good" and "bad" parents – supported by experts' discourse (Hays 1996, Saraceno 2016; Satta 2017) – have challenged the transformation of gender roles and the involvement of women in the job market, claiming for a costly involvement of women in childcare (Fargion 2021; Mortelmans 2021).

Some authors envision also shared custody law as a patriarchal backlash (Bimbi, Trifiletti 2006; Fleckinger 2022) that reflects discourses of the intellectual field in the legal field, supported by experts' discourse (e.g., currents of developmental psychology) and the movements of separated fathers (e.g., Rosen et al. 2009). The law apparently would aim to promote gender equality, but it does not properly consider the power relations in the family field that see women in a situation of

subordination, with lower economic and cultural capital than men and it shows a lack of protection for women and children, as confirmed by accounts from women participants to my study, gender specialists and lawyers. The legal field, in a power relation with the family field, seems to mainly support the reproduction of practices concerning the orthodox definition of the family. They offer particular constructions of parenthood and parenting, emphasizing parents' specific characteristics and (in)capacities, sanctioning, or rewarding certain relations of authority or subordination within family relations. The mainstream discourse on gender equality in the legal field seems to have scotomized the dynamics of power relations within the family field, imposing a reorganization that the family field cannot always incorporate (for a comparison, see also Sclater, Piper 2019).

In addition, the lack of adequate policy for single parents confirms a familist vision of the family (e.g., Bimbi 1997; Ruspini 2015) in which single parents and their families after separation are often trapped in a *triple bind* constituted by a combination of factors – inadequacies in resources, employment, and policies – that limit mothers' agency (Nieuwenhuis, Maldonado 2018; Tartari 2022).

With these structural conditions, separation can be interpreted as a phase of transition, a phase of generative disorientation, a phase of hysteresis in which the dominant doxa can be reconfirmed, or in which adaptation is managed, or in which heterodoxy – 'disagreement with mainstream assumptions about the way things' (Fram 2004, 556) – is embraced. At a macro-societal level, hysteresis happens amidst transformation of the traditional ways of conceiving, organizing, embodying family life (e.g., as the result of change in gender roles, or as a reaction to forms of familism that do not match with women's rights affirmation), in which sections of the legal and intellectual fields antagonize and propose different discourses (e.g., gender specialists against familist lawyers' discourse). It is the political action of the gender specialists in the intellectual/political field that supports the process of critical discussion of orthodoxy and explains how to embrace heterodoxy through forms of resistance or desistance to the field logics even if sometimes the costs for mothers are very high in terms of economic capital.

Some limitations of this paper reside first, in some aspects of the research design and approach of my study (i.e., a small sample for each country, the focus on women's standpoints which overshadows professionals' accounts and fathers' accounts); second, the analysis of emblematic cases that overshadows particular cases which would deserve attention. However, this analysis opens up possibilities to expand studies on the family as a field and its ruptures and to apply Bourdieu's theoretical tools to study the crises of the contemporary family.

Particularly exciting is the matter of the exploration of children's power in the family field (Atkinson 2014, 228–9) during separations and how they can subvert rules and parents' domination. Furthermore, a better understanding of how other fields work to support reproduction and change of the family field and how they contend for orthodox and heterodox definitions of the family might be extremely useful to stimulate not only academics' but also policy makers' reflections.

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